

separated, it was extracted with 3 × 5 ml portions of chloroform and concentrated to 5 ml. The concentrated solution (golden-yellow) was chromatographed over alumina. The first fraction, pale yellow, in colour, furnished the desired quinone (0.2 g., m.p. 240°–41° from acetic acid in orange coloured needles. Found C, 70.4; H, 4.0 C₁₈H₁₂O₅ reqd. C, 70.1; H, 3.9%. IR spectrum, 6.02 and 6.19μ [1,4-quinone]; 6.78, 7.44, 8.03, 8.33 and 8.81μ [methoxy group]).

Attempted synthesis of (6-hydroxy-3-methyl)-phenyl (2'-methoxy)-benzyl ketone :

o-Methoxyphenylacetic acid (1.5 g.) was dissolved in dry benzene (10 ml.) and thionyl chloride (3 ml.) was added to it. The acid chloride thus obtained was added to cold of ether (5 ml.) containing anhydrous aluminium chloride (0.66 g.) Freshly distilled *p*-cresylmethyl ether (1.1 g.) in dry ether (5 ml.) was added to it. The mixture was refluxed for 7 hr. and the product was decomposed in the usual manner, when a crystalline solid (0.08 g., m.p. 88°), was obtained. The product thus obtained gave a greyish-violet ferric reaction, but was alkali insoluble and failed to form a 2,4-DNP. However, the compound could not be obtained in analytically pure form.

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* Presently : Director, Indian Lac Research Institute, Namkum, Ranchi-10.

**Studies on Potential Pesticides—Part II
Synthesis of N-(2-Mercapto acetyl)-5-amino-
(substituted-aryl)-1,3,4 thiadiazolyl hydrazides
and N'-[(2-Mercapto acetyl)-5-amino substituted-aryl]-1,3,4 thiadiazolyl]-N⁴-
(phenyl)-3-semicarbazide**

A. K. SEN GUPTA & A. K. RAMRAKHYANI

Chemistry Department Lucknow University, Lucknow

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THIADIAZOLES and related compounds have found to possess biological activity in recent years¹⁻³. 2-Arylamino-5-mercapto thiadiazoles were shown to be pesticidal and fungicidal agents by

Giri *et al.*⁴ and Sen Gupta *et al.*⁵. Various hydroxides have been reported as antibacterial⁶ and fungicidal⁷ compounds. Gahon *et al.*⁸ have shown various semicarbazides to be more poisonous to caterpillars and other insects than deris dust. With a view to investigate the properties of compounds with these moieties we have synthesized several thiadiazoles. 2-Mercapto-5-arylamino 1,3,4-thiadiazoles were prepared by the cyclisation of aryl amino thiosemicarbazides. 2-Mercapto-5-amino (substituted aryl)-1,3,4-thiadiazolyl ethyl acetates were synthesized by the condensation of above thiadiazoles with chloro ethyl acetate. Hydrazides of the above esters were prepared and condensed with phenyl isocyanate to obtain the required semicarbazides.

Experimental

(All melting points are uncorrected).

Preparation of 2-Mercapto-5-amino (substituted aryl)-1,3,4-thiadiazolyl ethyl acetates :

A mixture of 2-Aryl amino-5-mercapto thiadiazole⁹⁻¹⁰ (0.01 mole), sodium hydroxide (0.01 mole) and chloro ethyl acetate (0.01 mole) in ethanol was heated on water bath for 2 hr. The product which was obtained by pouring the mixture in water was filtered and recrystallized from ethanol

The m.p., analytical data, yield are recorded in Table 1.

TABLE I

Sl. No.	R	M.P. °C	Yield %	Formula	Analytical data %	
					Found	Reqd.
1. Hydrogen		91	60	C ₁₂ H ₁₃ N ₃ O ₂ S ₂	C 48.46	48.81
					H 4.18	4.41
					N 14.06	14.24
2. 2-Methyl		60	60	C ₁₃ H ₁₅ N ₃ O ₂ S ₂	C 49.88	50.49
					H 4.21	4.85
					N 13.43	13.59
3. 3-Methyl		120	65	C ₁₃ H ₁₅ N ₃ O ₂ S ₂	C 49.65	50.49
					H 4.24	4.85
					N 13.63	13.59
4. 4-Methyl		96	60	C ₁₃ H ₁₅ N ₃ O ₂ S ₂	C 50.18	50.49
					H 4.36	4.85
					N 13.27	13.59
5. 2-Methoxy		106	60	C ₁₃ H ₁₅ N ₃ O ₃ S ₂	C 47.68	48.00
					H 4.08	4.62
					N 12.76	12.92
6. 4-Methoxy		112	50	C ₁₃ H ₁₅ N ₃ O ₃ S ₂	C 47.82	48.00
					H 4.36	4.62
					N 12.80	12.92
7. 2-Ethoxy		112	60	C ₁₄ H ₁₇ N ₃ O ₃ S ₂	C 48.94	49.56
					H 4.86	5.01
					N 12.44	12.39

NOTES

Preparation of *N*-(2-Mercapto-acetyl)-5-amino (aryl substituted) 1,3,4-thiadiazolyl hydrazides :

To a soln. of (0.01 mole) the appropriate ester in 15 ml of ethanol was added (0.01 mole) of 99% hydrazine hydrate. The reaction mixture was stirred for 0.5 hr then allowed to reflux on water bath for 0.5 hr and kept overnight. After cooling in an ice box, the crystalline mass was filtered and recrystallized from ethanol (see Table 2).

The m.p., yield and analytical data are recorded in Table 3.

TABLE 2

Sl. No.	R	M.P. °C	Yield %	Formula	Analytical data %	
					Found	Reqd.
1.	Hydrogen	165	75	C ₁₀ H ₁₁ N ₅ O ₂ S ₂	C 42.59 H 3.56 N 24.62	42.70 3.91 24.91
2.	2-Methyl	126	75	C ₁₁ H ₁₃ N ₅ O ₂ S ₂	C 44.61 H 4.23 N 23.44	44.75 4.40 23.73
3.	3-Methyl	172	70	C ₁₁ H ₁₃ N ₅ O ₂ S ₂	C 44.62 H 4.23 N 23.69	44.75 4.40 23.73
4.	4-Methyl	132	75	C ₁₁ H ₁₃ N ₅ O ₂ S ₂	C 44.28 H 4.59 N 23.71	44.75 4.40 23.73
5.	2-Methoxy	170	65	C ₁₁ H ₁₃ N ₅ O ₂ S ₂	C 42.06 H 4.17 N 22.62	42.44 4.18 22.51
6.	4-Methoxy	174	65	C ₁₁ H ₁₃ N ₅ O ₂ S ₂	C 42.18 H 4.06 N 22.43	42.44 4.18 22.51
7.	2-Ethoxy	132	65	C ₁₂ H ₁₅ N ₅ O ₂ S ₂	C 43.96 H 4.28 N 21.63	44.31 4.62 21.54

Synthesis of *N*'-[2-Mercapto acetyl]-5-amino (substituted-aryl)-1,3,4 thiadiazolyl]-*N*^A-(phenyl)-3-semicarbazides :

A mixture of (0.01 mole) of the hydrazide and (0.01 mole) of phenyl isocyanate was refluxed in 20 ml of dry benzene on water bath for 3 hrs and the mixture was allowed to stand overnight. A solid mass which separated out, was filtered and recrystallized from ethanol (see Table 3).

TABLE 3

Sl. No.	R	M.P. °C	Yield %	Mo. formula	Elemental Analysis%	
					Found	Reqd.
1.	3-Methyl Phenyl	168	65	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ N ₆ O ₂ S ₂	N 20.04	20.29
2.	4-Methyl Phenyl	179	65	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ N ₆ O ₂ S ₂	N 19.86	20.29
3.	3-Methoxy Phenyl	180	65	C ₁₈ H ₁₈ N ₆ O ₃ S ₂	N 19.27	19.53
4.	2-Ethoxy Phenyl	168	65	C ₁₉ H ₂₀ N ₆ O ₃ S ₂	N 18.63	18.92

The insecticidal activity of these compounds will be communicated later on as it is under investigation.

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